

Development of osseointegrative implants with drug delivery function for medical technology

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Abstract: Successful orthopaedic implant systems must restore the physical function of the affected joint or bone and promote bone regeneration. They must therefore have properties that come as close as possible to natural bone, i.e. have adapted mechanical and biocompatible behaviour. In addition to maintaining the physical functions, the patient-specific customisation of implants is playing an increasingly important role. Additive manufacturing processes offer an excellent starting point for this due to their high degree of design freedom. The integration of a drug delivery system using a modified bioprinting process supplements the customised implant with an antibacterial and bioactive component to prevent postoperative infections and promote bone growth.

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I. Introduction

Results of clinical studies show that one of the main risk factors for the occurrence of infections in humans after implantation is the implant used itself and its interactions with the surrounding tissue [1]. When it comes to adapting load-bearing medical implants even better to the needs of patients and their individual requirements in the future, there are several different approaches.

One possible option to improve the product behavior in contact with the tissue is to functionalize and redesign the surface. For this purpose, additively manufactured open-porous Ti-6Al-4V hybrid structures are used, which are functionalised by integrating antibacterial and bioactive agents (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Requirements profile for the development of a multifunctional load-bearing implant [2]

When implanted, the developed structures are exposed to an extreme load collective of mechanical, chemical and biological influences. In the following, the influence of the dynamic load and the associated microstructural fatigue in various states will be analysed and evaluated.

II. Material and methods

The hybride structures used in this study were made of titanium-based alloys Ti-6Al-4V grade 23 and were manufactured using additive manufacturing. The powder bed-based process of selective laser melting (SLM) enables the production of complex matrix structures due to its high design freedom. In the Concept Laser Mlab the samples were produced under a controlled argon inert gas atmosphere. These structures were designed in such a way that ingrowth of the bone is guaranteed with simultaneous stability in the load-bearing area. The hybrid structures consist of a combination of cubic space-centred, periodically repeating unit cells and a bulk material component (see figure 2).

Figure 2: Schematic model of the specimens consisting of bulk (grey) and cubic-space-centred unit cells, BCC (blue) for dynamic testing

Following the SLM process, the samples were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath with ethanol in several stages to remove particles from the inside auf the structures. Different microstructural states of the titanium-based alloy are to be taken into account for the dynamic investigations. Due to the process-related high quenching speeds in laser-

based additive manufacturing, a diffusionless martensitic transformation of the micro-melts takes place. This as-built state is to be compared microstructurally and dynamically with a heat-treated state. For this purpose, samples are subjected to a heat treatment at 800°C for two hours in an argon atmosphere and subsequent furnace cooling. The samples are then metallographically prepared on the bulk side in order to create a contact surface that is as free of defects as possible for the dynamic tests. The samples are dynamically tested in a servo-electric testing device. The tests are carried out in the pressure threshold range at a constant frequency of two hertz. The condition of an inserted sample is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: The experimental setup for dynamic testing of the sample

The samples should reach 10^7 cycles under these conditions to be considered fatigue resistant. A wöhler diagram to determine the fatigue strength is created from the specified path and the cycles resulting from the test.

III. Results and discussion

The following section presents and discusses the results achieved so far in the field of metallography and dynamic tests. As the tests on the heat-treated samples have not yet been completed, only the current status is presented here. The results of the heat-treated tests will be presented in further publications.

III.I. Metallographic results

The metallographic analyses of the different microstructures show clear differences between a conventionally manufactured sample and the additively manufactured samples.

While the conventionally manufactured samples made from a Ti-6Al-4V alloy can exhibit a bimodal $\alpha+\beta$ microstructure consisting of globular and lamellar microstructural components, the additively manufactured structures show completely different microstructures. The samples in the as-built state without additional forming show a mat-like microstructure of acicular martensitic α' phases. This significantly different picture can be explained by the greatly altered process conditions during additive manufacturing. Due to the solidification of the micro-melt produced in the process and the associated high quenching rates, the microstructure cannot develop according to the equilibrium conditions.

This rapid solidification under the influence of constitutional undercooling leads on the one hand to concentration shifts during the solidification of the micro-melt in the ternary system and on the other hand to the formation of the martensitic phase in the solid state. The

heat treatment carried out can reduce process-related residual stresses in order to increase the resistance of the samples to fatigue mechanisms under dynamic loading. The microstructure also shows a transformation of the martensitic α' phases to a lamellar structure of α and β phases.

III.II. Dynamic results

The dynamic tests on the untreated as-built samples indicate that a possible fatigue strength is achieved at approximately 0.1 mm (see figure 4).

Figure 4: Wöhler curve for as-built samples displacement-controlled at $f=2$ Hz

The individual tests showed that the force achieved in each cycle decreased over time. This results in an exponentially decreasing force curve. A comparison of the residual stresses measured by X-ray diffraction (XRD) shows that the dynamic loading during the tests leads to a reduction in the residual stresses in the structures. The kinetic energy introduced during the tests most likely triggers micromechanical processes leading to the initiation of diffusion and dislocation motions. In the case of excessive relaxation, these mechanisms lead to the formation of microcrack nuclei, which can be considered as the cause of the web fractures.

IV. Conclusions

Initial dynamic tests on specimens in the as-built specimens indicate a fatigue strength of the BCC specimens at approximately 0.1 mm for the displacement-controlled tests. Ongoing experiments on heat-treated samples indicate a fatigue strength at larger distances from approx. 0.2 mm. From the metallographic images it can be seen that the coarsening of the microstructure and the associated reduction in residual stresses during heat treatment leads to an improvement in the dynamic properties.

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